

Manufacturing and characterization of pvdf/ldpe thermoplastic composite using an island-in-a-sea fiber

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Abstract

Thermoplastic composite was prepared using poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) having piezoelectric property and low density polyethylene (LDPE). The PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber was prepared by melt conjugate spinning for ease of manufacture of the PVDF/LDPE thermoplastic composite. The LDPE and the PVDF were sea-component and island-component respectively. And the PVDF/LDPE thermoplastic composites were manufactured by a compression molding under the between melting temperatures of the PVDF and the LDPE. Through this process, the PVDF and the LDPE became a reinforcing fiber and a matrix of the composite, respectively. Composites were prepared in a variety of molding conditions. Manufactured the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and the PVDF/LDPE composites were characterized. Morphology of the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and the PVDF/LDPE thermoplastic composites were analysed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was used to determine the thermal characteristics. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was used to determine the crystalline characteristics. Finally, molding temperature of 110°C and molding time of 2min were identified as an optimal condition for molding process of the PVDF/LDPE composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

The PVDF is synthesized by addition polymerization of the $\text{CH}_2=\text{CF}_2$ monomer. When produced as the homopolymer (i.e. from 100% $\text{CH}_2=\text{CF}_2$ monomer), the majority of the PVDF chains have a regular structure of alternating CH_2 and CF_2 groups [1-2]. The PVDF is a polymer having a largest permittivity among the all crystalline polymers, and it is typical organic material showing unique electroactive properties, namely piezoelectric, pyroelectric and ferroelectric activities. Moreover, the PVDF have excellent mechanical properties, high chemical resistance, good thermal stability and processability. For that reason, the PVDF fiber has been studied since the 1960's [3-4]. The PVDF is polymorphic polymer, In other words, four kinds of different crystalline phase coexisted in the PVDF polymer, and they are classified as α , β , γ , δ and ϵ phases according to their crystalline structure. Among these crystalline phase, α and β -phase crystalline were most important. α -phase crystalline has TGTG (trans gauche trans gauche) structure, and it is non-polar structure. β -phase crystalline has TTTT (all trans) structure, it is parallel packing structure of trans form of molecular chain. Therefore, all of the permanent dipoles of the PVDF monomers are arranged in one direction and it causes increasing of spontaneous polarization. In general, content of α -phase crystalline is the highest in the PVDF polymer. However, by post-processing such as drawing and polarization, the PVDF molecules

are arranged orderly and they obtain the anisotropy. This results in an increase of β -phase crystalline and it improves the piezoelectric characteristics of the PVDF [5-7].

Fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite has been attracting attention due to various advantages such as recyclability, environment friendly, toughness and high-speed process. However, there are difficulties in the impregnation of thermoplastic composite manufacturing process. The molten viscosity of thermoplastic resins is extremely high compared to the solution viscosity of thermoset resins, which makes it difficult to impregnate thermoplastic resin into fiber bundles [8].

In this study, the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber was prepared by melt conjugate spinning for ease of manufacture of the PVDF/LDPE thermoplastic composite. And using this fiber, the PVDF/LDPE composites were manufactured by a compression molding under the between melting temperatures of the PVDF and the LDPE. Through this process, the PVDF and the LDPE became a reinforcing fiber and a matrix of the composite, respectively. Composites were prepared in a variety of molding conditions, and the optimal molding conditions were identified through the characterization. In the future, manufactured the PVDF/LDPE thermoplastic composites have undergone post-processing for development of piezoelectric properties. Finally various properties of the composite were analyzed and discussed.

2 EXperiments

2.1 Spinning of island-in-a-sea fiber

The materials used in this study were PVDF (Kynar720, Arkema) and LDPE (LDPE 737, Hanwha Chemical). The PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber was prepared by melt conjugate spinning at temperature of 270°C. Sea-component and island-component were LDPE and PVDF respectively. The number of island-component was 74, and the ratio of sea-component to island component was weight ratio of 5:5. Fiber was wound up at a speed of 750m/min and finally had a diameter of 47 μ m. Figure 1 shows the conjugate spinning process of island-in-a-sea fiber.

Figure 1: Schematics of conjugate spinning process of PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fibers.

2.2 Composite manufacturing

The PVDF/LDPE thermoplastic composites were prepared by a compression molding by using the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber. Process was carried out in a variety of time and temperature conditions between melting temperatures of the PVDF and the LDPE. Pressure was fixed at 500psi during the composite molding. Figure 2 shows the molding process of the PVDF/LDPE composite.

Figure 1: Schematics of PVDF/LDPE composite molding process using island-in-a-sea fibers.

2.4 Post-treatment

To increase the β -phase crystalline content in the PVDF/LDPE composites, drawing process was performed to the PVDF/LDPE composites manufactured under optimal molding condition.

2.4 Characterization

Morphologies of the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and its composites were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM)(S-4800, Hitachi). X-ray diffraction (XRD)(D/MAX-2200, Rigaku) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)(FTS-175C, USA) were used to determine the crystalline characteristics of the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and its composites and also, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)(DSC 1, Mattler-Toledo) was used to determine the thermal characteristics.

3 Results and discussions

Figure 3 and 4 show SEM images of the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and its composites. In the case of the PVDF/LDPE composite prepared at low temperature and short molding time, still it has a fibrous structure due to incomplete melting of the LDPE. With an increase in molding temperature and molding time, the LDPE phase was melted and bonded each other and became matrix of composite. But, at molding temperature of 112°C and time of 6min, composites have a distorted structure. When the viscosity of sea-component (LDPE) decreased with increase of temperature and time, the alignment of island-component (PVDF) was dispersed with flow of the LDPE. And it leads to non-uniform arrangement of fibers in matrix. Therefore, molding temperature of 110°C and molding time of 2min were identified as an optimal molding condition.

Figure 3: SEM image of PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber.

Figure 4: SEM images of PVDF/LDPE composites molded at temperature of (a) 105°C, (b) 110°C, (c) 112°C.

Figure 5 shows the DSC analysis results. DSC thermogram of the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber shows the endothermic peaks at 102°C, 165°C, and 167°C. 102°C, 165°C and 167°C represent the melting point of the LDPE, β -crystalline of the PVDF and α -crystalline of the PVDF, respectively. DSC thermogram of the PVDF/LDPE composites also shows the endothermic peaks at 102°C and 167°C. However, peak at 165°C was not observed. These results indicate the crystalline phase transition ($\beta \rightarrow \alpha$, $\beta \rightarrow \gamma$) of the PVDF by molding process. Increased α -phase crystalline can be transferred back to the β -phase crystalline having piezoelectricity by post-process.

Figure 5: DSC thermogram of PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and PVDF/LDPE composites.

Figure 6 shows the XRD analysis results. XRD pattern of the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and the PVDF/LDPE composites shows the peak at 18.4°, 20° and 21.4°. Peak at 21.4° represent crystalline of the LDPE. Peak at 20° represent β and γ -phase crystalline of the PVDF and peak at 18.4° represent α -phase crystalline of the PVDF. Peaks at 21.4° in the PVDF/LDPE composites extremely decreased compared to peak in the PVDF/LDPE fiber. This result indicates the decrease in crystallinity of the LDPE by manufacturing of composites. Peak at 18.4° increased. These results indicate the crystalline phase transition ($\beta \rightarrow \alpha$) of the PVDF with manufacturing of composite. But, decrease of peak at 20° is not significant. The reason is that peak of γ -phase crystalline and β -phase crystalline appears at same location. These results indicate the crystalline phase transition ($\beta \rightarrow \gamma$) of the PVDF during the manufacturing of composite. Increased α -phase crystalline can be transferred back to the β -phase crystalline having piezoelectricity by post-treatment.

Figure 6: XRD patterns of PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and PVDF/LDPE composites.

Also, FT-IR results of the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and the PVDF/LDPE composites show the change of crystalline phase by molding process. FT-IR spectrum bands at 1400cm^{-1} , 975cm^{-1} , 872cm^{-1} , 760cm^{-1} , 612cm^{-1} represent the α -phase crystalline and bands at 1278cm^{-1} , 840cm^{-1} represent the β -phase crystalline. Band at 1207cm^{-1} , 795cm^{-1} represent the γ -phase crystalline. After the manufacturing of composites, the band corresponding to β -phase crystalline was decreased, while the bands corresponding to α -phase crystalline and γ -phase crystalline were increased. These results indicate the crystalline phase transition ($\beta \rightarrow \alpha$, $\beta \rightarrow \gamma$) of the PVDF by molding process.

After post-treatment, FT-IR spectrum bands of β -phase crystalline increased, while the bands of α -phase crystalline decreased. These results indicate the crystalline phase transition ($\alpha \rightarrow \beta$) of the PVDF. This result is caused due to stretch of crystal structure by drawing process of composite. Increased β -phase crystalline in the composite by drawing may give the enhanced piezoelectric properties. This point would be discussed with the piezoelectric measurement of the composite.

4 Conclusions

In this study, the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber was prepared by melt conjugate spinning. And the PVDF/LDPE composites were manufactured by a compression molding. Composites were prepared in a variety of molding conditions. The PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and its composites were characterized by SEM, DSC, XRD and FT-IR analysis. Structure of the PVDF/LDPE island-in-a-sea fiber and structure of the PVDF/LDPE composites molded at various conditions were

observed by SEM. Crystalline characteristics and thermal characteristics were characterized by FT-IR, XRD and DSC, respectively. As a result, molding temperature of 110°C and molding time of 2min were identified as an optimal molding condition for manufacturing of the PVDF/LDPE thermoplastic composites. And, β -phase crystalline was changed to α -phase crystalline with manufacturing of composites. Changed α -phase crystalline can be transferred back to the β -phase crystalline having piezoelectricity by post-process such as drawing and poling. In this study, Prepared the PVDF/LDPE thermoplastic composites were treated by drawing process for development of piezoelectric properties. As a results, α -phase crystalline of the PVDF island component was changed to β -phase crystalline having piezoelectricity.

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